

Asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasini uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichlari

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Dolzarblik: hozirda elektr qurilmalarini nazorat qilish va boshqarishda yarim o'tkazgichli elementlardan keng foydalanilmoqda, bu esa elektr energiyaning sifat ko'rsatkichiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi nosimmetrik va nosinusoidal toklarning miqdorini oshishiga olib keladi. Nosimmetrik va nosinusoidal toklar elektr qurilmalarini reaktiv quvvatining oshishiga, haddan tashqari qizishiga, ish samaradorligini kamayishiga va tarmoqdagi boshqa qurilmalarning ish faoliyatiga ham salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Nosimmetrik va nosinusoidal toklarning miqdorini standartlarda belgilangan qiymatlardan oshmasligini ta'minlash muhim hisoblanadi.

Maqsad: asinxron motorlarda nosimmetrik va yuqori garmonika toklarini miqdorini filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalari orqali kompensatsiyalash va filtrlashda uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichidan olingan elektr signallar asosida nazorat qilish va boshqarish aniqligini, tezkorligini va ishonchligini oshirish hisobiga elektr energiyasining sifat ko'rsatkichlariga bo'lgan salbiy ta'sirlarni kamaytirishdan iborat.

Usullar: uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichi modelini ishlab chiqishda Proteus dasturidan foydalaniladi va CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali amaliy tadqiqot olib boriladi.

Natijalar: asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasini uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich yordamida nazorat qilish va boshqarish blogi, boshqaruv blokining qaror qabul qilish algoritmi ishlab chiqilgan. Proteus dasturida uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich chiqish signali asosida asinxron motorning stator toki va quvvat koeffitsientini aniqlash modeli yaratilgan va CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali manba kuchlanishi, asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichning chiqish kuchlanishi va ular orasidagi faza siljish burchagi grafiklari olinib tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: asinxron motor, reaktiv quvvat, filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi, tok o'zgartkichi, chiqish signali, fazalar siljish burchagi, yuqori garmonika, algoritim, sezgir element, induktiv element, sig'im element.

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Трёхфазные электромагнитные преобразователи тока фильтрокомпенсирующего устройства реактивной мощности асинхронного двигателя

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Актуальность: в настоящее время полупроводниковые элементы широко используются для контроля и управления электрическими устройствами, что приводит к увеличению количества несимметричных и несинусоидальных токов, влияющих на показатели качества электроэнергии. Симметричные и несинусоидальные токи также негативно влияют на увеличение реактивной мощности электроустановок, перегрев, снижение эффективности работы и работоспособности различных устройств в сети. Важно контролировать, чтобы величина симметричных и несинусоидальных токов не превышала значений, установленных стандартами.

Цель: компенсация токов несимметричных и высших гармоник в асинхронных двигателях фильтрокомпенсирующими устройствами, а также снижение их негативного влияния на показатели качества электроэнергии путём повышения точности, быстродействия и надёжности контроля и управления электрическими сигналами, получаемыми от трёхфазного электромагнитного преобразователя тока при фильтрации.

Методы: при разработке модели трехфазного электромагнитного преобразователя тока используется программное обеспечение Proteus, а тематическое исследование проводится с помощью устройства CASSYLAB.

Результаты: разработаны блоки управления и контроля фильтрокомпенсирующего устройства реактивной мощности асинхронного двигателя с помощью трехфазного электромагнитного преобразователя тока, алгоритм принятия решения блока управления. Программой Proteus на основе выходного сигнала трехфазного электромагнитного преобразователя тока была создана модель для определения тока статора и коэффициента мощности асинхронного двигателя, а с помощью устройства CASSYLAB были получены и проанализированы графики напряжения источника, выходного напряжения трехфазного электромагнитного преобразователя тока асинхронного двигателя и угла сдвига фазы между ними.

Ключевые слова: асинхронный двигатель, реактивная мощность, фильтрокомпенсирующее устройство, преобразователь тока, выходной сигнал, угол сдвига фаз, верхняя гармоника, алгоритм, чувствительный элемент, индуктивный элемент, емкостной элемент.

Three-phase electromagnetic current transducers of asynchronous motor reactive power filter-compensation device

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Relevance: currently, semiconductor elements are widely used in the control and management of electrical devices, which leads to an increase in the number of symmetrical and non-sinusoidal currents affecting the quality of electricity. Symmetrical and non-sinusoidal currents also negatively affect the increase in the reactive power of electrical installations, overheating, reduced operational efficiency and the operability of other devices in the network. It is important to ensure that the value of symmetrical and non-sinusoidal currents does not exceed the values set by the standards.

Purpose: to compensate for the magnitude of currents of symmetrical and high harmonics in asynchronous motors through filter compensating devices and reduce the negative impact on electricity quality indicators by increasing the accuracy, speed and reliability of monitoring and control based on electrical signals received from a three-phase electromagnetic current transducer during filtration.

Methods: when developing a model of a three-phase electromagnetic current transducer, Proteus software is used, and a case study is carried out using a CASSYLAB device.

Results: a control and control unit has been developed for a filter compensating device for reactive power of an asynchronous motor using a three-phase electromagnetic current transducer, an algorithm for making a decision of the control unit. In the Proteus program, based on the output signal of a three-phase electromagnetic current transducer, a model was created to determine the stator current and the power factor of an asynchronous motor, and using the CASSYLAB device, graphs of the source voltage, output voltage of a three-phase electromagnetic current transducer of an asynchronous motor and the phase shift angle between them were obtained and analyzed.

Keywords: asynchronous motor, reactive power, filter compensating device, current transducer, output signal, phase shift angle, upper harmonic, algorithm, sensing element, inductive element, capacitive element.

1. Kirish (Introduction)

Filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalari asosan induktiv va sig‘im elementlaridan tashkil topgan bo‘lib, garmonik buzilishlarning miqdori passiv, aktiv va gibrid filtrlar yordamida kamaytiriladi. Hozirda garmonik buzilishlarni filtrlashda yuqori ishonchlilik, samaradorlik, arzon narx va oddiy konfiguratsiyaga ega bo‘lganligi sababli passiv filtrlar keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Bundan tashqari passiv filtrlar yordamida reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiyalash ham mumkin. Odatda passiv filtrlar qarshilik, kondensator va induktiv elementlardan tashkil topadi va ularning ishlashi uchun tashqi quvvat manbai kerak bo‘lmaydi. Passiv filtrlarning ko‘plab turli topologiyalari mavjud bo‘lib, ko‘p hollarda parallel filtr konfiguratsiyasi eng afzal filtr topologiyalari hisoblanadi [1-4, 10]. Hozirgi kunda keng tarqalgan

filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi bu, takomillashtirilgan gibrid passiv filtr bo'lib, har bir faza uchun mos bo'lgan ketma-ket passiv va tiristorlar bilan boshqariladigan parallel passiv filtrlardan iborat. Takomillashtirilgan gibrid passiv filtrlar, an'anaviy gibrid filtrlarga nisbatan reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiya qilish va yuqori garmonikalarni filtrlash ko'rsatkichlari aniqroqdir [3, 12].

2. Materiallar va metodlar (Materials and Methods)

Har bir faza uchun mos, stator chulg'amlari joylashish tartibida pazlarga joylashtirilgan uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich signali asosida, takomillashtirilgan gibrid passiv filtrlar yordamida asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining nosimetrik va nosinusoidal toklari filtrlanadi va kompensatsiyalanadi. Bunda uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichdan chiquvchi kuchlanish signali mikroprotsessor (MK) yordamida belgilgan kattaliklar aniqlanadi, ya'ni yuqori garmonikalarning qiymatlari va nosimmetrik toklar sababli yuzaga keluvchi tarmoq kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanish signali orasidagi burchak [4-6, 13].

1-rasm. Asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasini uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich yordamida nazorat qilish va boshqarish

Fig.1. Control and management of the filter-compensation device of the asynchronous motor reactive power using a three-phase electromagnetic current Switch

Aniqlangan signallarga asosan mikroprotsessor boshqarish blokiga (BB) ma'lumotlarni yuboradi. Boshqarish bloki esa mikroprotsessordan kelgan signal asosida, birinchi tiristorli boshqarishli passiv fitr (TBPF1) va ikkinchi tiristorli boshqarishli passiv fitr (TBPF2) larni boshqaradi (1-rasm) [8,17-20].

2-rasm. Asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi boshqaruv blokining qaror qabul qilish algoritmi (0.4 kV kuchlanish uchun)

Fig.2. The decision-making algorithm of the control unit of the filter-compensation device of the asynchronous motor reactive power (for a voltage of 0.4 kV)

0.4 kV kuchlanish ta'minot manbaiga ulangan asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi quyidagi algoritmgaga asosan nazorat qilinadi va boshqariladi (O'zbekiston

Respublikasi Adliya vazirligining 1864-sonli nizomi va xalqaro elektr va elektronika muhandislari institutining IEEE 1159-2019 standartlariga asosan) [14, 18-22].

3-rasm. Asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi boshqaruv blokining qaror qabul qilish algoritmi (6÷10 kV kuchlanishlar uchun)

Fig.3. Asinxron motor jet power filter-compensation Device Control Unit decision-making algorithm (for voltages of 6÷10 kV)

Algoritimga asosan asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi boshqaruv blokining qaror qabul qilishi, umumiy garmonik buzilish THD_1 ning qiymati va quvvat parametrlarining nisbati $tg\phi$ orqali aniqlanadi (2-rasm).

1. ($THD_1 < 5\%$ va $tg\phi < 25\%$) Filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi normal rejimda ishlaydi, chunki garmonik buzilish va quvvat parametrlarining nisbati belgilangan me'yor oraliq'ida.

2. ($THD_1 < 5\%$ va $tg\phi > 25\%$) Filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasining har ikki tiristorli boshqarishli passiv filtrlari kompensator rejimda ishlaydi, chunki garmonik buzilish qiymati belgilangan me'yorda va quvvat parametrlarining nisbati esa belgilangan me'yordan yuqori.

3. ($THD_1 > 5\%$ va $tg\phi > 25\%$) Filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi filtr va kompensator rejimda ishlaydi, chunki garmonik buzilish va quvvat parametrlarining nisbati belgilangan me'yordan yuqori.

4. ($THD_1 > 5\%$ va $tg\phi < 25\%$) Filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi filtr rejimda ishlaydi, chunki garmonik buzilish qiymati belgilangan me'yordan yuqori va quvvat parametrlarining nisbati belgilangan me'yor oraliq'ida.

(6÷10) kV kuchlanish manbaiga ulangan asinxron motor reaktiv quvvatining filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmasi esa quyidagi algoritm orqali, $THD_1 < 5\%$ va $tg\phi < 30\%$ belgilangan me'yorlar asosida nazorat qilinadi va boshqariladi (3-rasm) [12, 13].

Asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich signali asosida quvvat koeffitsientini aniqlash:

Sezgir element xalqalarini turli ulanish sxemalariga ega asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichlaridan chiquvchi signallar va tarmoq kuchlanishlari fazalari orasidagi burchakning qiymatiga asosan asinxron motorning reaktiv quvvati kompensatsiya qilinadi [12, 15-19].

Stator tokini ifodalovchi chiqish kuchlanish signali va tarmoq kuchlanishi orasidagi burchak hamda stator tokining qiymatini matematik hisoblashda stator chulg'amlariga beriluvchi manba kuchlanishlari va sezgir elementdan chiquvchi kuchlanish ko'rinishidagi signallar, algebraik shaklga o'tkaziladi bunda asinxron motor statori har bir fazasidagi tokning aktiv va reaktiv tashkil etuvchi qiymatlari quyidagi formulalar orqali aniqlanadi [5-10, 21].

$$I_A = \frac{\left(\frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(-90^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(-90^\circ) \right) - \frac{w_4}{w_1} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_a - 90^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_a - 90^\circ) \right)}{R_{A,1} + jX_{A,1}}; \quad (1)$$

$$I_B = \frac{\left(\frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(30^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(30^\circ) \right) - \frac{w_5}{w_2} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_b + 30^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_b + 30^\circ) \right)}{R_{B,1} + jX_{B,1}};$$

$$I_C = \frac{\left(\frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(-210^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(-210^\circ) \right) - \frac{w_6}{w_3} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_c - 210^\circ) + j \cdot \frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_c - 210^\circ) \right)}{R_{C,1} + jX_{C,1}};$$

$$I_{A,aktiv} = \frac{\frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(-90^\circ) - \frac{w_4}{w_1} \cdot \frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_a - 90^\circ)}{R_{A,1} + jX_{A,1}}; \quad I_{A,reaktiv} = \frac{j \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(-90^\circ) - \frac{w_4}{w_1} \cdot \frac{U_{0,a}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_a - 90^\circ) \right)}{R_{A,1} + jX_{A,1}}; \quad (2)$$

$$I_{B,aktiv} = \frac{\frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(30^\circ) - \frac{w_5}{w_2} \cdot \frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_b + 30^\circ)}{R_{B,1} + jX_{B,1}}; \quad I_{B,reaktiv} = \frac{j \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(30^\circ) - \frac{w_5}{w_2} \cdot \frac{U_{0,b}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_b + 30^\circ) \right)}{R_{B,1} + jX_{B,1}};$$

$$I_{C,aktiv} = \frac{\frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(-210^\circ) - \frac{w_6}{w_3} \cdot \frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \cos(\beta_c - 210^\circ)}{R_{C,1} + jX_{C,1}}; \quad I_{C,reaktiv} = \frac{j \cdot \left(\frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(-210^\circ) - \frac{w_6}{w_3} \cdot \frac{U_{0,c}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sin(\beta_c - 210^\circ) \right)}{R_{C,1} + jX_{C,1}};$$

$$I_A = \sqrt{I_{A,aktiv}^2 + I_{A,reaktiv}^2}; \quad (3)$$

$$I_B = \sqrt{I_{B,aktiv}^2 + I_{B,reaktiv}^2};$$

$$I_C = \sqrt{I_{C,aktiv}^2 + I_{C,reaktiv}^2}.$$

Yuqoridagi formulalar orqali sezgir elementdan chiquvchi signalning qiymatiga asosan asinxron motorning statoridagi kuchlanish hamda tok kuchi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi quyidagicha topiladi.

$$\varphi_A = \left(90^\circ + \arctg \left(\frac{I_{A,reaktiv}}{I_{A,aktiv}} \right) \right); \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_B = \left(90^\circ + \arctg \left(\frac{I_{B,reaktiv}}{I_{B,aktiv}} \right) \right);$$

$$\varphi_C = \left(90^\circ + \arctg \left(\frac{I_{C,reaktiv}}{I_{C,aktiv}} \right) \right).$$

CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali amaliy tadqiqot ishlari olib borildi, unga asosan 4AA63A4Y3 tipli qisqa tutashgan rotorli asinxron motorning nominal ish rejimida manba kuchlanishi, asinxron motor uch fazali tok o'zgartkichi kuchlanish signali va ular orasidagi faza siljish burchagi aniqlandi.

Tadqiqot natijasida amaliy aniqlangan ma'lumotlar va yuqorida keltirilgan ifodalar asosida Proteus dasturida uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichi signali asosida asinxron motor statorining toki va quvvat koeffitsientini aniqlash modeli yaratildi, buning uchun Arduino UNO mikrokontrolleridan foydalanildi (4-rasm). Manba kuchlanish parametrlarini aniqlashda kuchlanish transformatori yordamida kuchlanish miqdori kamaytirildi, bir fazali to'g'irlagich sxemasi orqali Arduining analog piniga ulandi, bu orqali mikrokontroller yordamida manba kuchlanishini bilish imkoniyati mavjud bo'ldi. Bundan tashqari operatsion kuchaytirgich orqali manba kuchlanishining faza siljish burchagini bilish uchun zero cross nuqtalari aniqlandi.

Asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichdan kuchlanish ko'rinishida chiquvchi signalning parametrlarini aniqlashda ham manba kuchlanish parametrlarini aniqlash sxemalaridan foydalanildi va uning kuchlanish qiymati va faza siljish burchagi aniqlandi. Manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanish faza siljish burchagining farqini aniqlashda XNOR mantiqiy elementdan foydalanildi va undan chiquvchi signal Arduining raqamli piniga ulandi. Manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanishi parametrlari va yuqoridagi formulalarga asosan Arduino IDE da stator toki va quvvat koeffitsientini aniqlash dastur kodi yozildi va aniqlangan parametrlar LCD 16x4 monitorga uzatildi. LCD monitorida manba kuchlanishi, asinxron motorning statoriga joylashtirilgan sezgir elementdan chiquvchi kuchlanish, asinxron motor statorining toki va asinxron motorning quvvat koeffitsienti joy olgan (A faza uchun) [3, 12, 19-21].

Asinxron motorning stator pazlariga joylashtirilgan sezgir elementdan kuchlanish ko'rinishida chiquvchi signalning qiymati, asinxron motorning statorida hosil bo'lgan tokning qiymatiga proporsionaldir.

4-rasm. Proteus dasturida, uch fazali elektromagnitli tok o'zgartkich signali asosida asinxron motorning stator toki va quvvat koeffitsietini aniqlash modeli

Fig. 4. In the Proteus program, a model for determining the stator current and power coefficient of an asynchronous motor based on a three-phase electromagnet current Switch signal

3. Natijalar (Results)

Uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich chiqish signallari asosida asinxron motorning reaktiv quvvatiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi yuqori garmonika toklari quyidagicha aniqlandi (1-Jadval) [12, 14, 17].

1-Jadval. Asinxron motorning reaktiv quvvatiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi yuqori garmonika toklari

Table 1. High harmonic currents affecting the reactive power of the asynchronous motor

k	Tok transformatori, I_a (A)	Har bir faza uchun mos bitta sezgir element xalqali uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich, U_a (V)	Har bir faza uchun mos ikkita sezgir element xalqa-larga ega, ketma-ket ulangan uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich, U_a (V)	Har bir faza uchun mos ikkita sezgir element xalqa-larga ega, parallel ulangan uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich, U_a (V)	Har bir faza uchun mos ikkita sezgir element xalqa-larga ega, differensial ulangan uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich, U_a (V)
1	0,8996	2,4948	2,4635	4,9577	4,9326
3	0,0410	0,1924	0,2343	0,3034	0,2963
5	0,0192	0,0363	0,0376	0,0431	0,0512
7	0,0074	0,0443	0,0543	0,0267	0,0264
9	0,0036	0,1267	0,0823	0,0524	0,0473
11	0,0039	0,0442	0,0387	0,0184	0,0182
13	0,0020	0,0053	0,0442	0,0106	0,0104
15	0,0013	0,0029	0,0054	0,0078	0,0068
17	0,0010	0,0042	0,0056	0,0061	0,0052
19	0,0007	0,0016	0,0033	0,0053	0,0042
21	0,0000	0,0024	0,0031	0,0047	0,0037
23	0,0000	0,0005	0,0052	0,0036	0,0025
25	0,0000	0,0009	0,0055	0,0043	0,0027
27	0,0000	0,0005	0,0053	0,0033	0,0023
29	0,0000	0,0019	0,0034	0,0030	0,0020
31	0,0000	0,0017	0,0011	0,0011	0,0011
33	0,0000	0,0006	0,0037	0,0006	0,0005
35	0,0000	0,0004	0,0030	0,0012	0,0011
37	0,0000	0,0013	0,0020	0,0018	0,0017
39	0,0000	0,0004	0,0044	0,0017	0,0016
41	0,0000	0,0003	0,0028	0,0017	0,0015
43	0,0000	0,0004	0,0006	0,0017	0,0014
45	0,0000	0,0006	0,0013	0,0021	0,0019
47	0,0000	0,0006	0,0032	0,0015	0,0014
49	0,0000	0,0009	0,0012	0,0006	0,0005

Bir vaqtning o'zida filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalari yuqori garmonika toklarini filtrlash va reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiyalash uchun ishlatiladi. Asosan filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalarida induktiv va sig'im elementlaridan tashkil topgan o'zaro ketma-ket va parallel ulangan gibrid passiv filtrlardan foydalaniladi. Parallel passiv filtrlar chiziqli bo'lmagan yuklama toklarini filtrlash va kompensatsiyalash uchun mos kelsa, ketma-ket passiv filtrlar esa chiziqli bo'lmagan kuchlanishlarni filtrlash uchun ishlatiladi. Shuning uchun gibrid passiv filtrlar bir vaqtning o'zida reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiyalaydi va garmonik buzilishlarni filtrlaydi [10-15, 18].

Bir vaqtning o'zida filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalari yuqori garmonika toklarini filtrlash va reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiyalash uchun ishlatiladi. Asosan filtr-kompensatsiya qurilmalarida induktiv va sig'im elementlaridan tashkil topgan o'zaro ketma-ket va parallel ulangan gibrid passiv filtrlardan foydalaniladi. Parallel passiv filtrlar chiziqli bo'lmagan yuklama toklarini filtrlash va kompensatsiyalash uchun mos kelsa, ketma-ket passiv filtrlar esa chiziqli bo'lmagan kuchlanishlarni filtrlash uchun ishlatiladi. Shuning uchun gibrid passiv filtrlar bir vaqtning o'zida reaktiv quvvatni kompensatsiyalaydi va garmonik buzilishlarni filtrlaydi [10-15, 18].

4. Muhokama (Discussion)

CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali 4AA63A4Y3 tipli qisqa tutashgan rotorli asinxron motorning nominal ish rejimida aniqlangan ma'lumotlari keltirilgan (A faza uchun). Bunda U_A -A faza manba kuchlanishi, U_a -A faza uchun mos asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichidan kuchlanish ko'rinishida chiquvchi signal, I_A -asinxron motorning stator toki (A faza), β -manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi (5-rasm). Asinxron motor statorining A fazasidagi tokning qiymati $I_1=0.91$ A, shu faza uchun mos, xalqalari differensial ulangan sezgir elementidan chiqqan kuchlanishning qiymati $U_a=4.56$ V va manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi $\beta=-9.92^\circ$ aniqlandi (A faza manba kuchlanishining boshlang'ich fazasi $\alpha=0^\circ$ deb oligan) [5-10, 12].

Proteus dasturida 4AA63A4Y3 tipli qisqa tutashgan rotorli asinxron motorning nominal ish rejimidagi A faza manba kuchlanishi, A faza uchun mos asinxron motor uch fazali tok o'zgartkichidan kuchlanish ko'rinishida chiquvchi signal, manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi aniqlandi (6-rasm). Asinxron motorning A fazasidagi tokning qiymati $I_1=0.9$ A, shu faza uchun mos sezgir elementdan chiqqan kuchlanishning qiymati $U_a=4.6$ V va manba kuchlanishi va chiqish kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi $\beta=-9.89^\circ$ aniqlandi (A faza manba kuchlanishining boshlang'ich fazasi $\alpha=0^\circ$ deb oligan) [15-20, 13].

5-rasm. CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali aniqlangan manba kuchlanishi, asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichining chiqish kuchlanishi va ular orasidagi faza siljish burchagi grafiklari (A faza uchun)

Fig.5. The source voltage determined by the CASSYLAB device, the output voltage of the asynchronous motor three-phase electromagnetic current Switch, and the Phase Shift angle graphs between them (Phase A)

6-rasm. Proteus dasturi orqali aniqlangan manba kuchlanishi, asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichning chiqish kuchlanishi va ular orasidagi faza siljish burchagi grafiklari (A faza uchun)

Fig.6. The source voltage determined by the Proteus program, the output voltage of the asynchronous motor three-phase electromagnetic current Switch, and the Phase Shift angle graphs between them (A for Phase)

Tok o'zgartkichdan chiquvchi kuchlanish signali asosida quyidagi kattaliklar aniqlandi. Tadqiqotlar asinxron motorning A fazasi misolida ko'rib chiqildi.

Asinxron motor stator tokining qiymati:

1. $I_A=0.87$ A, Katalogdagi qiymat.
2. $I_A=0.91$ A, CASSYLAB qurilmasi yordamida amaliy aniqlangan qiymat.
3. $I_A=0.9$ A, Proteus dasturida aniqlangan qiymat.

Asinxron motorning quvvat koeffitsientining qiymati:

1. $\cos\varphi=0.65$, Katalogdagi qiymat.
2. $\cos\varphi=0.653$, CASSYLAB qurilmasi yordamida aniqlangan qiymat.
3. $\cos\varphi=0.65$, Proteus dasturida aniqlangan qiymat.

Manba kuchlanishi va uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich chiqish kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagi qiymatlari:

1. $\beta_1=-9.92^\circ$, CASSYLAB qurilmasi yordamida aniqlangan qiymat.
2. $\beta_1=-9.89^\circ$, Proteus dasturida aniqlangan qiymat.

Asinxron motor sezgir elementidan chiquvchi kuchlanishning qiymati:

1. $U_a=4.56$ V, CASSYLAB qurilmasi yordamida aniqlangan qiymat.
2. $U_a=4.6$ V, Proteus dasturida aniqlangan qiymat.

Yuqoridagi 5-rasm va 6-rasmlarda keltirilgan natijalarni tahlil qilsak, uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichni chiqish kuchlanishi qiymati, manba kuchlanishi va asinxron motor stator chulg'ami qarshiliklari o'zgarmagan holda stator chulg'amidan o'tayotkan tok kuchiga bog'liq funksiya ekanligini ko'ramiz. Asinxron motor manba kuchlanishining o'zgarish holatida chiqish signalining qiymati tokiga va quvvat koeffitsientiga proporsionalligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

5. Xulosa (Conclusions)

Asinxron motorning ish davri mobaynida yuklama qiymatining oshishi uning stator tokining oshishiga, bu esa chiqish kuchlanishi bilan manba kuchlanishi orasidagi faza siljish burchagining oshishiga, chiqish kuchlanishini va quvvat koeffitsientini kamayishiga olib keldi. Bundan ko'rinadiki manba kuchlanishi bilan sezgir elementdan chiquvchi kuchlanish orasidagi faza siljish burchagining oshishi quvvat koeffitsientini kamayishiga sabab bo'ladi. Asinxron motor uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkich signali orqali asinxron motor stator tokining qiymati va quvvat koeffitsienti yuqoridagi tadqiqotlar orqali tahlil qilindi. CASSYLAB qurilmasi orqali asinxron motorning sezgir elementidan chiquvchi kuchlanish qiymati va manba kuchlanishi bilan faza siljish burchagi amaliy topildi. Aniqlangan qiymatlar asosida Proteus va Arduino dasturlari yordamida asinxron motorning stator tok kuchi va quvvat koeffitsientini aniqlash modeli ishlab chiqilib uch fazali elektromagnit tok o'zgartkichning chiqish kuchlanishi va ular orasidagi faza siljish burchagi grafiklari olindi.

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